

MEDICAL SCIENCES

STRUCTURAL SPECIFICITY OF AXODENDRITIC PROJECTIONS OF PSEUDOUNIPOLAR NEURONS AND ITS INTERACTION WITH SURROUNDING SATELLITE GLIAL CELLS.

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Abstract

We present structural properties of projections of pseudounipolar neurons of the spinal ganglia (sensory dorsal root ganglia). Taken into account neurons composing these ganglia have only one processes by name axodendritic, and then latter branched into central and peripheral parts. The long peripheral processes receive different afferent stimuli from outer and inner environment, whereas the short central processes project into the dorsal horn of the spinal cord. This work was to learn the morphological (histological and ultrastructural) properties of axodendritic processes and its interaction with surrounding satellite glial cells. The research performed on male rat's dorsal root ganglia containing blocks that prepared according to general methods accepted in microscopy. The current study demonstrates that the axodendritic processes - the place, involving in reception and transmission of nerve impulses; also, the neuron and its branches - axoplasmic protrusion (axodendritic processes) completely surrounded by a satellite glial cells; in the axoplasm of this projection the number of cytoskeletal elements (microtubules, neurofilaments) is too high, in spite of the absence of chromatophilic substance.

Keywords: pseudounipolar neuron, axodendritic projection, satellite glial cell, electron microscope

Introduction. The dorsal root ganglion (also named spinal ganglia, sensory root ganglia) has a major clinical application, principally in its association with neuropathic pain. The pseudounipolar neurons composing mentioned ganglia with their processes aid in dorsal and ventral roots of the spinal nerves, carrying sensory messages from many receptors, including those for pain and temperature towards the central nervous system for a reply [1]. A properly study structural peculiarities of that neurons and its processes help to improve the diagnosis and treatment of neuropathic pain syndromes. An important feature of the pseudounipolar neurons composing the spinal ganglia is that they surrounded by satellite glial cells from all sides. Satellite glial cells in peripheral nervous system covered not only neurons also their processes. One of the areas that not studied in detail in the literature is the incomplete clarification of connections satellite glial cells and pseudounipolar neurons at the level of axodendritic projections.

Aim of study was to carefully investigation the morphological structural properties of axodendritic projections of neurons of spinal ganglia and its interaction with the surrounding satellite glial cells.

Material and methods. The object of study was dorsal root ganglia purchased from 20 white male rats with a weight of 200 - 230 grams that fed a standard laboratory in specific pathogen-free facilities. All procedures complied with the Principles of Laboratory and Animal Care established by the Azerbaijan Medical University. The experimental animals divided into two groups. After of the intravenous injection (into the tail vein 0.5 ml physiological salt solution) the first groups of research animals decapitated under ketamine/xylazine (100/10 mg/kg) anaesthesia; the abdominal and thoracic cavity of the rats opened by parasternal incision, and then was taken out the internal organs and the vertebral bodies were cut. Later by the help of special lancet, a spinal canal opened and spinal ganglions removed from the soft tissue at intervertebral foramen level. The specimen had been fixated in solution that contains 2% paraformaldehyde, 2% glutaraldehyde and 0.1% picric acid prepared in phosphate buffer (pH 7.4). The second groups of research animals were deeply anaesthetized with ketamine (Nembutal) and perfused transcatheterially with a solution containing 2% formaldehyde, 2% glutaraldehyde and 0.1% picric acid prepared in phosphate buffer (pH 7.4). 2 hour later

after intravascular fixation, a spinal canal had opened and dorsal root ganglions removed from the soft tissue. The specimen taken from both groups animals after the postfixation in 1% osmium acid solution in phosphate buffer, prepared into Spurr and Araldit-Epon blocks according to general methods accepted in microscopy [2]. Obtained from blocks on ultratomes LKB-III, Leica EM UC7 semithin sections (thickness 1-2 μ m) stained with methylene blue, azure II and basic fuchsin or with toluidine blue [3]. Then carefully inspected images of each section recorded by using Pixera (USA) digital camera connected to Latimet (Leitz) microscope and saved in computer. Silver and gold ultrathin sections from same blocks first painted with 2% uranyl acetate

solution, then in 0.6% lead citrate made in NaOH 0.1N solution. Then ultrathin sections examined under the Transmission Electron Microscope (JEM-1400, Japan) at an accelerating voltage of 80-100 kV and received the electronograms. This procedure continued until the block had been used. The morphometric data of the image taken in TIF format (microphotographs and electronograms) analyzed using the "Olympus Soft Imaging Solutions" computer program (The TEM imaging platform) by German company.

Results. We should note that the majority of more than studied 10,000 nerve cells composing the spinal ganglia have a free covering satellite glial cells [4].

Figure 1. Microscopic (A) and ultrastructural (B) slide.

A - Semithin section of pseudounipolar neuron (by red arrow shown axodendritic processes); B - electronogram of two neighbor pseudounipolar neurons (by red star shown axodendritic processes). Explanation given in text. Stain: A - methylen blue, azur II and basic fuchsin; B – uranyl acetat and lead citrate. Abbreviation: N-neuron, SGC satellite glial cell, n-nucleus, AdP- axodendritic processes. Magnification: A 20 μ m, B 2400 time.

As can be seen from the picture (figure 1A) the neuron with a diameter of 55 μ m (that is large light neuron) has nucleus, nucleolus and large cytoplasm. On slide in the middle upper part of the neuron arising one axodendritic projection (marked by red arrow), which coiled in left side as arch, as well as, on the right side from it visible the two its segments located separately. All 3 part of processes of pseudounipolar neurons whole covered by satellite glial cells and isolated from surrounding connective tissue elements. It should be noted that such protrusions are rarely found in the semithin section of studied neurons. Other interesting peculiarities on the picture 1A the fact that the protrusion itself has light staining cytoplasm and stand out from

the body of nerve cells by its intensity. On figure 1B shown two neighbor pseudounipolar neurons that possess their whole covering individual glial cells, like "cap" on top. Also on the upper part of both neurons, visible axodendritic processes (marked by red star), that intensity is differ from cell body of neuron. Neuronal cell body contain nucleus with prominent nucleolus, organelles, cytoskeletal elements, but in its projection only visible some organelles, such as mitochondrion and dense cytoskeletal elements. Both neuron and projection isolated from external connective tissue structural elements by satellite glial cells (on figure 1B shown by red arrow).

Figure 2. Electronogramma (ultrastructural slide, both A and B) of axodendritic processes of pseudounipolar neuron. Explanation given in text. Stain: (both A and B) uranyl acetate and lead citrate. Abbreviation: N- neuron, SGC- satellite glial cell, AdP- axodendritic processes, M - mitochondrion (shown by red arrow). Magnification of both 2µm.

Ultrastructural examination of the axodendritic protrusions of pseudo unipolar neurons (figure 2A) under more magnification shows that the number of cytoskeletal elements (microtubules, neurofilaments) is too high, despite the absence of chromatophilic substance with synthetic function. The conducted morphometric study shows that cytoskeletal elements dominate in the cytoplasm of the initial part of axodendritic protrusions. Despite the sharp densification of cytoskeletal elements, the number of mitochondria appears to be significantly lower (figure 2A). However, another noteworthy point is that mitochondria are located mainly near glial cell-covered parts of the axolemma (figure 2B). The location of mitochondria at the level of the neuroglial border suggests that there is a high physiological activity accompanied by energy expenditure in

the places where the axodendritic projections of the pseudounipolar nerve cell begin. A similar structure - few numbers round shaped lightly staining (transparent), looks like separately isolated structure on the right side of neuron with a diameter of 65 µm on figure 3A, that indicated by red arrow and named axodendritic processes. The analysis of the obtained histological slides shows that this transparency of the axodendritic processes is due to the absence of chromatophilic substance (Nissl substance, that makes up the synthetic apparatus of the nerve cell). As a confirmation of the above, the cytoplasm of the projection part staining in light color separated from the surrounding connective tissue elements by satellite glial cells. In the electronogram, satellite glial cells covering these processes are very prominent (figure 3B).

Figure 3. Microscopic (A) and ultrastructural (B) slide. A - Semithin section of pseudounipolar neuron with its branching axodendritic processes (shown by red arrows). B - electronogramma of bundle of the branching axodendritic processes of pseudounipolar neurons. Explanation given in text. Stain: A - methylene blue, azur II and basic fuchsin; B - uranyl acetate and lead citrate. Abbreviation: N - neuron, n-nucleus, SGC-satellite glial cell, AdP- axodendritic processes, CTE- connective tissue elements. Magnification: A 20µm, B 2µm.

Apparently, the neuron and the branches of its axoplasmic protrusion (axodendritic processes) completely surrounded by a satellite glial cell. Interestingly, the nucleus of the satellite glial cell is located between the axoplasmic protrusion and not around the neuron. Electronograms obtained from serial ultrathin sections of the same region (figure 3B) show that each of the above-described neuron and its surrounding axodendritic projections has a distinct satellite glial coating.

At the level where the glial sheath covers either the part of neuron or its various projections, the mesaxon and similar structure characteristic for myelinated and unmyelinated nerve fibers are not detected (fig. 1B; fig. 2B, 3A, 3B). This once again shows that satellite glial cells cover not only the bodies of pseudounipolar neurons, but also their axodendritic projections and the initial parts of the its branches (fig. 1B, 2B) arised from neuron.

In the literature, some authors suggested that satellite glial cells belong to the cells with a lot of number processes, like astrocytes (surrounding nerve cells in the CNS) [5]. But based on the materials we have studied, we can come to the following results:

1. While the feet of astrocytes form the glial border resting on the inner surface of the pia mater, the corresponding structure is generally not found in the spinal ganglia;

2. While the projections of astrocytes cover only parts of nerve cells where no synaptic connections, but satellite glial cells surround pseudounipolar cells body and their projections from all sides;

3. Although astrocytes also form a glial sheath (blood-nerve barrier) around cerebral vessels, but spinal ganglia satellite glial cells generally do not have projection that are in close contact with vessels. Thus, although the satellite glial cells of the spinal ganglia aid to the cells with processes, but there is no homology between them and astrocytes.

Conclusion. Summarizing the obtained materials, it should be noted that the axodendritic processes arised from pseudounipolar neuron have coiled around latter.

Despite of cytoplasm of neuron, the axoplasm devoid of Nissle substance. Axodendritic processes contain a lot of number cytoskeletal elements (microtubules, neurofilaments) and the mitochondria (which are the synthesis center of macroergic molecules) are located in the axoplasmic protrusions in close to the plasmalemma of satellite glial cells shows that they are actively involved in the reception and transmission of nerve impulses.

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References

1. Ahimsadasan N, Reddy V, Kumar A. Neuroanatomy, Dorsal Root Ganglion. [Updated 2021 Sep 7]. In: StatPearls [Internet]. Treasure Island (FL): StatPearls Publishing; 2022 Jan
2. Electron Microscopy. Methods and Protocols. Edited by John Kuo. // USA, Totowa, New Jersey: Humana Press Inc., 2007, 608 p.
3. D'Amico F. A polychromatic staining method for epoxy embedded tissue: a new combination of methylene blue and basic fuchsine for light microscopy // Biotech. Histochem., 2005, v.80, No 5-6, pp. 207-210.
4. Aliyarbayova A.A., Gasimov E.K., Shahmamedova A.I., Sadiqova G.H.. Morphological peculiarities of interaction neurons and satellite glial cells in dorsal root ganglia. A light and electron microscopic study // The 1st International scientific and practical conference "Modern science: problems and innovations" (April 5-7, 2020) SSPG Publish, Stockholm, Sweden. 2020. Pp. 45-50.
5. Hanani, M. Satellite glial cells in sensory ganglia: from form to function // Brain Research Reviews, 2005, 48(3):457-76